

In Vitro Effect of Ceftazidime-Avibactam by Synergy Testing with Aztreonam using Disc E Strip Method - Contribution of Promising Combination in the Era of Antibiotic Resistance

Borgohain A¹, Rangaiah, A², Rangappa KG³

¹Post Graduate, Department of Microbiology, Bangalore Medical College and Research Institute

²Professor, Department of Microbiology, Bangalore Medical College and Research Institute

³Lecturer, Department of Microbiology, Bangalore Medical College and Research Institute

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Corresponding Author: Dr. Borgohain A

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Abstract:

Introduction: Carbapenem resistant Enterobacterales (CRE) is a rapidly unfolding concern in the realm of public health. Ceftazidime-Avibactam combination has excellent in vitro activity against Gram negative pathogens showing promising results with Aztreonam.

Objective: To determine the phenotypic synergy of Ceftazidime-Avibactam with Aztreonam in Carbapenem resistant Enterobacterales.

Methodology: 100 Carbapenem resistant Enterobacterales were included in the study and tested for Ceftazidime-Avibactam (CZA) sensitivity by Vitek2 using Critical Alert cards. Phenotypic synergy testing of CZA resistant isolates with Aztreonam (ATM) was done by Disc-E strip method. ATM discs were placed 15mm away from centre of CZA strip and incubated overnight at 37°C. Reduction in MIC of CZA by ≥ 3 folds and zone of inhibition around ATM >21 mm was reported as synergy positive. Isolates were further tested for presence of genes coding for bla-NDM and bla-OXA-48 by conventional PCR.

Results: 62/100 (62%) isolates were *Klebsiella pneumoniae* and 38/100 (38%) were *Escherichia coli*. 61/62 (98%) *Klebsiella pneumoniae* and 36/38 (94%) *Escherichia coli* isolates were synergy positive. 1 (2%) *Klebsiella pneumoniae* and 2 (6%) *Escherichia coli* were synergy negative. PCR identified bla-NDM gene in 46(46%), bla-OXA-48 in 21(21%), co-production of both in 27(27%) isolates. 6(6%) isolates were negative for both genes.

Conclusion: Multidrug resistance is a threat to mankind and this combination of Ceftazidime-Avibactam with Aztreonam will help in combating this problem.

Keywords: Ceftazidime-Avibactam, Aztreonam, Multidrug resistance, Carbapenem resistant Enterobacterales, Disc E strip test, Synergy.

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Introduction

In tertiary care hospitals the pervasive challenge of Multi-Drug Resistance (MDR) has become a pressing issue. Notably, the surge of Carbapenem resistance has reached concerning levels presenting as a formidable challenge. Carbapenem resistance is exemplified by *Klebsiella pneumoniae* and *Escherichia coli* which are the most commonly occurring species with resistance.

Owing to their broad spectrum activity, Beta-lactams exhibit excellent efficiency against Gram negative pathogens. However, their role in MDR pathogens is diminishing due to very high prevalence of enzymes like extended spectrum beta lactamases (ESBLs), Metallo-beta-lactamases (MBLs), Amp C beta lactamases and OXA-48 producing pathogens. In many centres, MDR

pathogens have the combinations of these enzymes, so therapeutic options are very limited. [1] Beta lactamases act by hydrolysing the β -lactam ring which is invariably found in all beta lactams. [2] The emergence of carbapenem-resistant Enterobacteriaceae (CRE) is a rapidly evolving global public health dilemma and calls for urgent action within the international scientific community. [3]

Ceftazidime-avibactam is an intravenously administered combination of the third-generation cephalosporin Ceftazidime and the novel, non- β -lactam β -lactamase inhibitor Avibactam. Ceftazidime-avibactam has excellent in vitro activity against many important Gram-negative pathogens, including many extended-spectrum β -

lactamase, Amp C, *Klebsiella pneumoniae* Carbapenemase producing Enterobacteriaceae. Aztreonam is a monobactam antibiotic. The metallo-beta-lactamases (MBL) like NDM cannot destroy Aztreonam. But ESBLs and other enzymes inactivate the antibiotic. [4] Whereas, Ceftazidime-avibactam can act against ESBL and with Aztreonam exhibit clinical efficacy in treating bacteraemia resulting due to MBL producing CRE. Therefore, prioritizing CRE for testing susceptibility to CZA-ATM combination becomes inevitable. [5]

Materials and Methods

This prospective study was conducted in the Microbiology laboratory at a tertiary care hospital. Clinical samples like blood, pus, urine, sputum, wound discharge, ascitic fluid, pleural fluid received in the laboratory for culture and antimicrobial susceptibility testing were processed according to laboratory protocol. Identification and antimicrobial susceptibility testing was done by using Vitek2 (bioMerieux, India) compact system. Enterobacteriales- *Klebsiella pneumoniae* and *Escherichia coli*, that were resistant to one or more of the Carbapenem antibiotics (Meropenem, Imipenem, Ertapenem) tested were considered as CRE. Further MIC for Ceftazidime-Avibactam was detected by using Critical alert cards. Ceftazidime-Avibactam resistant isolates were subjected for synergy test with Aztreonam. Disc-E strip synergy testing was done by using Mueller-Hinton agar plates (150mm diameter).

Test isolate was lawn cultured on MHA plates and E strip of Ceftazidime-Avibactam (E-TEST®, bioMerieux, USA) was placed on the plate and Aztreonam disc (30 mcg, HiMedia, Mumbai, India) was placed at a distance of 15mm from the E test strip such that centre of disc remain parallel to the cut-off sensitivity mark of Ceftazidime-Avibactam (8 µg/mL)(12). The plate was incubated for 18-24 h at 37° Celsius. Interpretation of the test was done according to CLSI M100, 2023. An inverted-D shape or reduction of MIC ≥ 3 folds for Ceftazidime-Avibactam as well as zone diameter of > 21mm for Aztreonam disc was reported as positive for synergy. The isolates were further subjected for conventional PCR to detect the presence

of genes like bla-NDM and bla-OXA-48 coding for Carbapenemases.

Polymerase Chain Reaction (PCR) for Carbapenemase gene detection

The genes analyzed for Carbapenemase production in this study were NDM and OXA-48. Conventional PCR was performed.

DNA extraction

DNA was extracted from fresh overnight incubated plates having well isolated colonies emulsified with 300µl of sterile distilled water. Sample were incubated at 100°C for 15 minutes and centrifuged at 13,000rpm for another 15minutes. Supernatant was utilized for DNA extraction.

Primers

Primers used in the reaction are described in Table no. 1. Commercial primers were obtained from Sakhala Enterprises, Bengaluru.

Polymerase Chain Reaction mixtures

Conventional PCR was performed to detect NDM and OXA-48 genes. The amplicon size for NDM and OXA-48 genes were 83 bp and 438 bp, respectively. The master mix (DNTPS, Buffer, MgCl₂, Primers) was obtained from Sakhala Enterprise, Bengaluru. PCR mixtures were prepared under laminar flow under strict precautions to prevent cross contamination. Reagents and reaction mixtures for 50µl assay were used.

Amplification was carried out with the following thermal cycling profile: initial denaturation for 5 min at 95°C, 35 cycles of amplification consisting of 30 s at 95°C, 30 s at 45°C, and 30 s at 72°C, with 5 min at 72°C for the final extension

Gel electrophoresis

Gel electrophoresis was carried out in 1X Tris-acetate-EDTA using 1.5% agarose gel.

Results and interpretation

The gel was viewed under ultraviolet transilluminator and was documented with the help of digital camera attached to the computer. Specific bands at particular gene amplicon size were considered as positive PCR reaction.

Table 1: Primers used for polymerase chain reaction to detect genes coding for Carbapenemase production

Primer	Sequence	Gene	Size of PCR product (bp)
NDM (F)	CATTAGCCGCTGCATTGATG	NDM	83
NDM (R)	GTCGCCAGTTTCCATTTGCT		
OXA-48(F)	GCGTGGTTAAGGATGAACAC	OXA-48	438
OXA-48(R)	CATCAAGTTCAACCCAACCG		

Results

A total of 100 Carbapenem resistant Enterobacteriales were included in the study.

Among them 62 isolates were *Klebsiella pneumoniae* and 38 isolates were *Escherichia coli* (Fig.1). All isolates were resistant to Ceftazidime-Avibactam.

from pus, 8 (13%) from sputum, 5 (8%) from urine. Out of 38 *Escherichia coli* isolates, 16 (42%), 12 (32%), 7 (18%), 3 (8%) were from blood & body fluids, pus, sputum, urine respectively.

Out of 62 *Klebsiella pneumoniae* isolates, 28 (45%) were from blood and body fluids, 21 (34%) were

Table 2: Distribution of carbapenem-resistant *Klebsiella pneumoniae* and *E. coli* among clinical specimen

Specimen	<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i> isolates	<i>E.coli</i> isolates	Total number of isolates
Blood & Body fluids	28	16	44
Pus	21	12	33
Sputum	8	7	15
Urine	5	3	8
Total	62	38	100

61/62 (98%) *Klebsiella pneumoniae* isolates and 36/38 (94%) *Escherichia coli* isolates were positive for synergy (Fig.2). MIC of all isolates for CZA remained between 16 - 64 µg/mL.

0.5, 0.75, 1, 2, 2, 16 µg/mL respectively. Majority of isolates showed >3folds reduction in MIC for CZA confirming synergy (Fig.3). 1 (2%) *Klebsiella pneumoniae* and 2 (6%) *Escherichia coli* were negative for synergy. PCR identified bla-NDM gene in 46 (46%) isolates, bla-OXA-48 in 21(21%) isolates, co-production of NDM and OXA-48 in 27(27%) isolates and 6 (6%) isolates were negative for both NDM and OXA-48 (Fig.4&5) Number of isolates at each MIC (µg/mL) for each antimicrobial Agent.

Disc E strip test with Aztreonam showed MIC of CZA in the ranges 2- 0.125µg/mL.

Among the *Klebsiella pneumoniae* isolates, 4, 2, 9, 6, 13, 23, 2, 2, 1 isolates showed MIC of 0.125, 0.25, 0.38, 0.5, 0.75, 1, 2, 2, 16 µg/mL respectively. Similarly for *Escherichia coli*, 3, 2, 3, 5, 8, 11, 4, 0, 2 showed MIC of 0.125, 0.25, 0.38,

Table 3: Comparison of MIC of ceftazidime-avibactam by Disc E strip test and Vitek-2 sensitivity

Isolate category	Antimicrobial agent	MIC (µg/mL)											Vitek2 MIC(µg/mL)for CAZ-AVI		
		0.125	0.25	0.38	0.5	0.75	1	1.5	2	4	8	16	>16	>32	>64
Both (100)	CAZ-AVI	7	4	12	11	21	34	6	2			3	62	22	16
<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i> (62)	CAZ-AVI	4	2	9	6	13	23	2	2			1	42	13	7
<i>Escherichia coli</i> (38)	CAZ-AVI	3	2	3	5	8	11	4	0			2	20	9	9

Figure 1: Carbapenem resistant *Klebsiella* and *E.coli* isolates

Figure 2: Results of synergy shown by Carbapenem resistant Klebsiella and E.coli isolates

Figure 3: Disc- E strip synergy test showing more than 3 folds reduction in MIC of Ceftazidime-Avibactam with susceptibility to Aztreonam disc

Figure 4: Conventional PCR for NDM (base pair length-83bp) and OXA-48 (base pair length-438bp)

Figure 5: Presence of NDM and OXA-48 genes in the Carbapenem resistant Klebsiella pneumoniae and Escherichia coli isolates

Discussion

The problem of Multidrug resistance is now a global phenomenon increasing day after day. The cause for this is multifactorial. Amongst the MDR bacteria, Carbapenem resistant Enterobacteriales (CRE) have become ubiquitous now. CRE has unfortunately become resistant to a number of combination antibiotics as well leaving us with only a handful of drugs to treat them with. In our study we included 100 Carbapenem resistant isolates from various clinical isolates, amongst which 62% were Klebsiella pneumoniae and 38% were Escherichia coli. All these isolates were resistant to Ceftazidime-Avibactam. By Disc E Strip method, majority of Klebsiella pneumoniae (98%) showed synergy when Ceftazidime-Avibactam with Aztreonam was used in combination. Our results are in congruence with the results of a study conducted by Sahu et al. where 41 (82%) out of 48 Klebsiella pneumoniae isolates showed synergy by Disc E strip method followed

by Pseudomonas aeruginosa, 24(70%) and Escherichia coli, 9 (29%) out of total 153 samples. [1]

Wenzler et al found similar results. Synergy was observed between CAZ/AVI E- test and ATM disc in 79 (98.75%) out of 80 Klebsiella pneumoniae isolates and in 19 (95%) out of the 20 Escherichia coli isolates by Disc E strip method. [6]

In a recent study by Sreenivasan et al, all 60 isolates initially were resistant to CZA and ATM individually by both disc diffusion and E strip method but showed synergy to combination of CZA+ATM. [7]

Marshall et al in 2017 evaluated the same combination where 21 MBL positive isolates were resistant to CZA but in combination with Aztreonam 17 out of those 21 resistant isolates showed susceptibility by disk diffusion method and a reduced agar dilution MIC shown by all 21 isolates. [9]

Table 4: Comparison of synergy in present study with previous literature

Author	% of Synergy in KP isolates	% of Synergy in E.coli isolates
Sahu et al [1]	82%	29%
Wenzler et al [6]	98.75%	95%
Sreenivasan et al [7]	63.3%	18.3%
Marshall et al [9]	33%	19%
Present study	98%	94%

In our current study, we also found bla-NDM (46%) gene as the predominant gene followed by bla-OXA-48(21%) and a combination of both (27%). These results align closely to the findings of the study by Sahu et al. [1], Mohanty et al. [3], Sreenivasan et al.[7], Taha R et al.[8], Sader et al.[11], where NDM was the resistant gene in 96%, 76.3%, 41.6%, 91.25%, 33.3% of the isolates respectively. In this study, majority of the Carbapenem resistant strains was notably high in blood specimens followed by pus which amplifies

concerns for the healthcare workers in doling out effective treatment. Additionally, Carbapenem resistant urine, sputum samples further complicate the management and patient care leaving the healthcare worker with only a handful of treatment options. The frequency with which CRE is being isolated at hospitals serves as an obvious sign of a silent pandemic which is now swiftly coming into prominence, demanding stringent action and prevention. Although it is a laborious, time consuming process requiring manpower and

expertise [10], CLSI has now recommended broth disk elution method for this combination. Out of 140,000 healthcare-associated Enterobacteriaceae infections per year, more than 9,000 are caused by CRE (urgent threat level). An alarming finding from a molecular characterization study of carbapenem resistant Enterobacteriaceae in Mumbai, West India, revealed that 18.5% (21/113) of the clinical isolates investigated possessed dual Carbapenemase genes [13]

In current study, 1 *Klebsiella pneumoniae* and 2 *Escherichia coli* tested negative for synergy. The reason for this could be due to other resistance mechanisms like amino acid substitutions at active site of beta-lactamases or due to decreased membrane permeability. [14]

Altered Penicillin Binding Protein (PBP) can also compromise the efficacy of Ceftazidime hindering overall synergy and eventually, leading to treatment failure with this drug combination. [15] Six isolates that did not yield presence of any resistant genes but showed synergy could be due to genes other than NDM and OXA-48 responsible for the resistance to Ceftazidime-Avibactam. In instances when resistance is mediated by mechanisms unrelated to MBL production, synergy or certain gene detection may not reveal study-specific results.

In resource-constraint settings where high end instruments are scarce due to prohibitive costs, our study accordingly aimed to detect synergy by Disc E strip method followed by PCR for gene detection.

Conclusion

The dangers of multidrug resistance loom over global public health challenging the efficacy of existing antimicrobial drugs and overall therapeutic domain. In this regard, our findings of synergy seem like a beacon of hope. The combination of Ceftazidime-Avibactam with Aztreonam has potential to restore effectiveness of antimicrobial therapy against multidrug resistant organisms. The implications of our study enhance capacity to combat these resistant pathogens saving countless lives and safeguarding the wellbeing of mankind.

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